

Impact of Company Income Tax and Value Added Tax on Corporate Investment in the Nigerian Telecommunications Industry

Olalekan Nurudeen SHEHU¹, Iwundu Chinyere KENNEDY², Olusegun Reuben ADENIKINJU³
and Godwin Emmanuel OYEDOKUN⁴

¹Team Lead & Senior Manager Tax, Large Tax Audit (Oil & Gas) Upstream, Nigeria Revenue Services, Ikoyi, Lagos, Nigeria; habiluv@yahoo.com || +234 703 657 8194

²Department of Accounting, Faculty of Business Management and Sustainability (BMS), ICT University Cameroon. kennedy.chinyere@ictuniversity.edu.cm, kendy4real2000@yahoo.com +2348037866998
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5038-618x>

³Managing Director, Procuremasters Ltd., Chesham, Buckinghamshire, England, nuges77@yahoo.com; || +234 8068185137, || +447867903007

⁴Department of Management and Accounting, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria, godwin.oyedokun@lcu.edu.ng; godwinoyedokun@yahoo.com || +234 803 373 7184
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8317-3924>

Abstract

This study examines the impact of Company Income Tax (CIT) and Value Added Tax (VAT) on corporate investment within the Nigerian telecommunications industry, a sector widely recognized as a critical driver of economic growth, digital transformation, and infrastructural development. The study adopts a quantitative research design, utilizing secondary data obtained from eight (8) listed telecommunications and ICT-related firms in Nigeria over the study period. Data were analysed using multiple regression techniques estimated through Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) to evaluate the nature and significance of the relationship between taxation variables and corporate investment. The empirical findings reveal that Company Income Tax (CIT) exhibits a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with corporate investment, suggesting that higher corporate tax burdens may discourage investment, although not in a strongly determinative manner. Conversely, Value Added Tax (VAT) demonstrates a positive but statistically insignificant relationship with corporate investment, indicating that consumption-based taxation does not significantly hinder investment decisions within the sector. Overall, the results imply that while taxation plays a role in shaping investment behaviour, it is not a primary determinant of corporate investment in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. The study concludes that non-tax factors

such as macroeconomic stability, infrastructure availability, regulatory certainty, and access to finance exert a more substantial influence on investment decisions. It recommends that policymakers adopt a holistic approach to investment promotion by improving the business environment, rather than relying solely on tax adjustments.

Keywords: Company income tax, Corporate investment, Nigerian telecommunications Industry, Taxation policy, Value added tax

Word count: 232

Introduction

In recent decades, developing economies particularly in Africa have intensified efforts to create investment-friendly environments capable of stimulating sustainable economic growth and development. Central to these efforts is the design and implementation of effective tax systems that not only generate adequate government revenue but also support private sector expansion and capital formation. Taxation remains one of the most critical fiscal instruments available to governments for financing public expenditure, redistributing income, and correcting market inefficiencies (Nnubia et al., 2020; Stantcheva, 2021). However, the challenge for policymakers lies in striking an optimal balance between revenue generation and the promotion of investment, as excessive or poorly structured taxation can discourage business expansion and reduce overall economic productivity (Adeyeye, 2019; Egbuhuzor & Adokiye, 2021).

In Nigeria, taxation plays a pivotal role in national development, providing the financial resources required for infrastructure, healthcare, education, and security (Kaka, 2020; Olatunji & Oluwatoyin, 2019). Nevertheless, concerns persist regarding the efficiency, multiplicity, and burden of taxes imposed on businesses, particularly in capital-intensive sectors. Empirical evidence suggests that high tax rates and complex tax structures may deter investment by reducing firms' disposable income and limiting their capacity to reinvest in productive assets (Agbarakwe, 2019; Babu et al., 2020). Consequently, understanding the relationship between taxation and corporate investment is essential for designing policies that foster economic growth without undermining business incentives.

The Nigerian telecommunications industry provides a compelling context for examining this relationship. Since the liberalisation of the sector in the early 2000s, telecommunications has emerged as a key driver of economic transformation, facilitating digital connectivity, financial inclusion, and innovation across multiple sectors (Kujore et al., 2021; Umukoro et al., 2021). Despite its strategic importance, the sector faces significant fiscal challenges, including multiple taxation from federal, state, and local authorities. Telecommunications firms are reportedly subject to over thirty different taxes and levies, which increase operational costs and may ultimately be transferred to consumers, thereby affecting service quality and market expansion (Kujore et al., 2021; Raimi et al., 2022).

Among the various forms of taxation, Companies Income Tax (CIT) and Value Added Tax (VAT) are particularly significant due to their direct and indirect effects on corporate financial performance and investment decisions. CIT, imposed on corporate profits, directly affects retained earnings and the internal financing capacity of firms, which are critical determinants of investment (Akadakpo & Akogo, 2022; Freebairn, 2022). Conversely, VAT, as a consumption-based tax, influences pricing structures and demand patterns, with potential implications for revenue generation and investment planning (Odunsi, 2022; Oraka et al., 2017). While CIT is often associated with a negative impact on investment due to its effect on profitability, VAT may exhibit a more neutral or mixed effect depending on its incidence and administration.

Theoretically, the relationship between taxation and investment can be explained through frameworks such as the Ability-to-Pay Principle and the Free Cash Flow Theory. The Ability-to-Pay Principle emphasises equity and fairness in taxation, advocating that entities with greater financial capacity should bear a higher tax burden (Dougherty et al., 2019; Kjærsgaard, 2021). However, excessive tax burdens may distort investment incentives. Similarly, the Free Cash Flow Theory posits that firms rely on internally generated funds for investment decisions; thus, higher taxes that reduce free cash flow may constrain investment activities (Jensen, 1986; Njuguna et al., 2022).

Empirical studies on the nexus between taxation and investment present mixed findings. While some studies report a negative relationship between corporate taxes and investment (Agbarakwe,

2019; Sankarganesh & Shanmugam, 2023), others find insignificant or context-dependent effects, suggesting that non-tax factors such as infrastructure, regulatory quality, and macroeconomic stability may play a more dominant role (Yusuf & Mohd, 2020; Freebairn, 2022). In the Nigerian context, these inconsistencies highlight the need for sector-specific analysis, particularly in industries like telecommunications that are highly sensitive to regulatory and fiscal policies.

Against this backdrop, this study investigates the impact of Companies Income Tax (CIT) and Value Added Tax (VAT) on corporate investment in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. By focusing on a sector that is both economically strategic and heavily taxed, the study seeks to provide empirical insights that can inform fiscal policy reforms aimed at enhancing investment, improving sector performance, and sustaining economic growth. The specific objectives are to examine the effect of CIT on corporate investment and to assess the impact of VAT on investment decisions within the industry.

Literature Review

The literature on taxation and corporate investment reflects a rich interplay between fiscal policy instruments and firm-level decision-making, particularly within developing economies such as Nigeria. This section synthesises conceptual, theoretical, and empirical contributions relevant to the impact of Company Income Tax (CIT) and Value Added Tax (VAT) on corporate investment, with a specific focus on the telecommunications sector.

Corporate investment is broadly conceptualised as the allocation of financial resources to projects with the expectation of future returns. It encompasses capital expenditures, research and development, acquisitions, and other strategic outlays that enhance firm value (Panagiotidis & Printzis, 2021). As noted by Njuguna et al. (2022), corporate investment decisions significantly influence firm valuation, stakeholder confidence, and long-term sustainability. Firms typically finance such investments through internal sources, such as retained earnings, or external sources, including debt and equity financing (Ososuaqpor, 2016). Given resource constraints, firms must optimise investment decisions to maximise returns and ensure continuity.

Taxation plays a dual role in modern economies: it is both a revenue-generating mechanism for governments and a policy tool capable of influencing economic behaviour. Governments rely on tax revenues to provide public goods and services, maintain macroeconomic stability, and promote development (Nnubia et al., 2020; Laura, 2019). In developing countries, taxation is particularly critical for reducing dependence on external financing and fostering domestic resource mobilisation (Oladipo et al., 2019). However, the structure and administration of taxes can significantly affect private sector activities, including investment decisions.

Company Income Tax (CIT), a direct tax imposed on corporate profits, is widely regarded as a key determinant of investment behaviour. High CIT rates may reduce after-tax returns on investment, thereby discouraging capital formation (Adeyeye, 2019). Conversely, moderate and predictable tax regimes can enhance investor confidence and stimulate investment. In Nigeria, CIT is governed by the Companies Income Tax Act, which imposes a standard rate of 30% on large companies, with reduced rates for small and medium-sized enterprises (Akadakpo & Akogo, 2022). Despite its importance as a revenue source, concerns have been raised regarding its potential distortionary effects on investment decisions.

Value Added Tax (VAT), on the other hand, is an indirect consumption tax levied at each stage of the production and distribution chain. Unlike CIT, VAT is generally borne by the final consumer, although firms act as intermediaries in its collection (Odunsi, 2022). Theoretically, VAT is considered neutral with respect to production decisions, as it does not directly tax profits. This neutrality suggests that VAT may have a less pronounced effect on corporate investment compared to direct taxes. However, in practice, the administrative burden and cash flow implications of VAT compliance can influence firm behaviour (Oraka et al., 2017).

The Nigerian telecommunications sector provides a particularly relevant context for examining the interaction between taxation and investment. Since the liberalisation of the sector in the early 2000s, telecommunications have become a critical driver of economic growth, facilitating connectivity, innovation, and digital transformation (Umukoro et al., 2021). Despite its growth, the sector faces significant challenges, including multiple taxation and regulatory inconsistencies. Kujore et al. (2021) observe that telecommunications firms in Nigeria are subject to numerous

federal, state, and local levies, which increase operational costs and discourage investment. This multiplicity of taxes often leads to inefficiencies, including service disruptions and reduced infrastructure expansion.

Theoretically, the relationship between taxation and investment is anchored in several frameworks. The Ability-to-Pay Principle posits that tax burdens should be distributed according to taxpayers' capacity, promoting equity and social justice (Kjærsgaard, 2021). While this principle supports progressive taxation, it may inadvertently affect investment incentives if high-income firms face excessive tax burdens. The Free Cash Flow Theory, advanced by Jensen (1986), provides further insight by suggesting that taxation can influence the availability of internal funds for investment. Higher tax liabilities reduce free cash flow, potentially constraining investment, while lower taxes may increase managerial discretion, sometimes leading to inefficient investment decisions.

Empirical evidence on the relationship between taxation and corporate investment remains mixed. Babu et al. (2020) find that both CIT and VAT have significant negative effects on private investment in Sub-Saharan Africa, suggesting that high tax burdens deter capital formation. Similarly, Agbarakwe (2019) reports an inverse relationship between corporate taxes and private sector investment in Nigeria. These findings are consistent with neoclassical investment theory, which posits that higher taxes reduce the marginal efficiency of capital.

Conversely, some studies report positive or insignificant relationships. Yusuf and Mohd (2020) find that CIT has a positive short-run effect on domestic investment in Nigeria, while VAT exhibits a negative long-run impact. Turakpe et al. (2020) also document a positive relationship between taxation and investor performance, suggesting that the impact of taxes may depend on broader economic conditions and the utilisation of tax revenues. Freebairn (2022) further argues that the effect of corporate taxation on investment is moderated by financing structures, indicating that the relationship is more complex than traditionally assumed.

Sector-specific studies highlight additional nuances. Anika and Obidimma (2021) emphasise the regulatory challenges associated with taxing telecommunications companies in Nigeria, advocating for sector-specific tax policies. Nwabachili (2020) critiques the Nigerian tax system

for overburdening firms, thereby discouraging investment and economic growth. These studies underscore the importance of aligning tax policy with sectoral dynamics to promote sustainable development.

Overall, the literature reveals no consensus on the direction or magnitude of the relationship between taxation and corporate investment. While theoretical models generally predict a negative relationship, empirical findings vary depending on context, methodology, and the specific taxes examined. This divergence highlights the need for context-specific studies, particularly in sectors such as telecommunications, where taxation interacts with regulatory, infrastructural, and technological factors.

In summary, the literature establishes that taxation is a critical determinant of corporate investment, but its effects are mediated by a range of institutional and economic variables. The Nigerian telecommunications sector, characterised by rapid growth and complex tax structures, provides a compelling case for further empirical investigation into the impact of CIT and VAT on investment decisions.

Theoretical Review

The theoretical foundation of this study is anchored on the Ability-to-Pay Principle and the Free Cash Flow (FCF) Theory, both of which provide critical insights into how taxation influences corporate investment decisions. These theories offer complementary perspectives by addressing, respectively, the fairness of tax burden distribution and the behavioural implications of taxation on managerial decision-making and resource allocation.

The Ability-to-Pay Principle is a fundamental doctrine in public finance which posits that taxation should be imposed based on the taxpayer's capacity to bear the burden, irrespective of the direct benefits received from government expenditure (Kjærsgaard, 2021). This principle underpins progressive taxation systems, where higher-income entities are expected to contribute a larger proportion of their earnings to public revenue. In the context of corporate taxation, particularly Company Income Tax (CIT), this principle justifies higher tax obligations for more profitable

firms, with the aim of promoting equity and redistributing income within the economy (Dougherty et al., 2019).

From an investment perspective, the Ability-to-Pay Principle has both positive and negative implications. On one hand, it supports government revenue mobilisation, which can be channelled into infrastructure development, security, and institutional improvements that enhance the investment climate (Osho & Efuntade, 2019). On the other hand, excessive tax burdens on profitable firms may reduce retained earnings, thereby limiting internal financing available for investment. This may discourage capital formation, especially in capital-intensive sectors such as telecommunications. Furthermore, high tax rates may incentivise tax avoidance strategies, distort economic decisions, and reduce overall efficiency within the economy (Ojeka, 2011).

Complementing this perspective is the Free Cash Flow Theory, propounded by Jensen (1986), which provides a firm-level explanation of how taxation affects investment behaviour. The theory defines free cash flow as the residual cash available to a firm after funding all positive net present value (NPV) projects. According to Jensen (1986), managers in firms with substantial free cash flow may engage in suboptimal investment decisions, such as overinvestment in low-return projects, due to agency conflicts between management and shareholders.

Taxation, particularly CIT, plays a significant role in shaping free cash flow. Higher corporate taxes reduce the amount of disposable income available to managers, thereby limiting the potential for wasteful expenditure and agency costs. In this sense, taxation can serve as a disciplinary mechanism that constrains managerial opportunism (Njuguna et al., 2022). However, this same reduction in free cash flow may also constrain a firm's ability to finance profitable investment opportunities, particularly in environments where access to external finance is limited. This is especially relevant in developing economies like Nigeria, where financial markets are less developed and firms rely heavily on internally generated funds.

The Free Cash Flow Theory also highlights the role of financial structure in investment decisions. Firms with limited free cash flow may resort to external financing, such as debt, which introduces additional monitoring mechanisms through debt covenants. While this may improve efficiency, it

also increases financial risk and may deter investment in uncertain economic conditions. Conversely, lower tax burdens may increase free cash flow, providing firms with greater flexibility to invest in growth-enhancing projects, although this may also increase the risk of inefficient capital allocation.

When considered together, the Ability-to-Pay Principle and Free Cash Flow Theory provide a comprehensive framework for analysing the relationship between taxation and corporate investment. The former emphasises equity and macroeconomic objectives, while the latter focuses on efficiency and firm-level behaviour. In the Nigerian telecommunications sector, where firms face multiple tax obligations alongside significant capital requirements, these theories help explain the complex and often ambiguous effects of CIT and Value Added Tax (VAT) on investment decisions.

In summary, while taxation is essential for revenue generation and economic development, its design and implementation must strike a delicate balance between equity and efficiency. Excessive tax burdens may stifle investment by reducing available funds, whereas well-structured tax policies can promote accountability, discipline managerial behaviour, and create an enabling environment for sustainable corporate investment.

Empirical Review

Empirical literature on the relationship between taxation and corporate investment presents mixed but insightful evidence, reflecting variations across countries, sectors, and methodological approaches. A growing body of studies has examined how Company Income Tax (CIT) and Value Added Tax (VAT), alongside other macroeconomic variables, influence investment decisions.

Babu, Pantaleo, and Ndanshau (2020) investigated the impact of taxation and selected macroeconomic variables on private investment in Sub-Saharan Africa, focusing specifically on countries within the East African Community (EAC) and Southern African Development Community (SADC). Employing a dynamic neoclassical investment framework and estimating the model using the One-Step Difference Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), the study found that both CIT and VAT exert a statistically significant and negative effect on private

investment. The findings suggest that higher tax burdens reduce the incentive for capital formation within the region. Additionally, the study identified real interest rates as a critical determinant of investment levels, with higher rates discouraging investment. Interestingly, credit to the private sector, although statistically significant, exhibited a negative and theoretically inconsistent relationship with investment, suggesting structural inefficiencies in financial intermediation. The authors recommended a reduction in corporate tax rates and the adoption of accommodative monetary policies to stimulate investment inflows.

In the Nigerian context, Turakpe, Azoroh, Tordee, and Effe-Nnamdi (2020) examined the effect of taxation on investors' performance using data from ten listed firms over the period 2009–2019. Adopting a quasi-experimental design and applying Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression techniques, the study explored the relationship between CIT, return on equity, and dividend per share as a proxy for investors' performance. The results revealed that CIT, when combined with firm performance indicators, positively influences dividend payouts and, by implication, investor returns. This finding suggests that taxation does not necessarily undermine investor performance when firms are able to generate sufficient returns. The study emphasized the importance of incorporating tax considerations into dividend policy decisions and called on government to utilize tax revenues effectively to create a more conducive business environment.

Similarly, Agbarakwe (2019) conducted an empirical analysis of the impact of corporate taxation on private sector investment and economic development in Nigeria using time series data spanning 1980 to 2017. Applying OLS multiple regression analysis, the study found that both CIT and VAT have negative and statistically significant effects on private sector investment. The results indicate that increases in these taxes are associated with reductions in investment levels, thereby constraining economic growth. The study concluded that high tax rates may discourage capital accumulation and recommended tax reforms aimed at reducing the burden on firms to stimulate investment and enhance economic development.

Yusuf and Mohd (2020) provided further insight by examining the effect of taxation on domestic investment in Nigeria using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach. Their model incorporated multiple tax variables, including personal income tax (PIT), CIT, and

VAT, alongside macroeconomic indicators such as interest rates, stock market capitalization, and foreign direct investment. The findings revealed a nuanced relationship: PIT exhibited a significant positive effect on investment in both the short and long run, while VAT had a significant negative impact in the long run. CIT, on the other hand, showed a positive but short-run effect on investment. These mixed results underscore the complexity of tax-investment dynamics and suggest that the impact of taxation depends on the type of tax and the time horizon considered. The study recommended improvements in infrastructure, macroeconomic stability, and financial access as complementary measures to enhance investment.

Beyond Nigeria, Sankarganesh and Shanmugam (2023) examined the effect of corporate income tax on investment decisions of manufacturing firms in India using panel data from 2005 to 2019. Utilizing static panel estimation techniques, the study found that effective corporate tax rates have a negative and statistically significant impact on corporate investment. However, the estimated tax elasticity of investment was relatively low, indicating that while taxation matters, its quantitative effect may be smaller compared to other determinants. The study also found that the adverse impact of taxation is more pronounced in private firms and varies across economic cycles, being stronger in pre-crisis periods. These findings highlight the importance of firm-specific and macroeconomic conditions in moderating the tax-investment relationship.

Freebairn (2022) approached the issue from a financial structure perspective by analysing how company income tax affects business investment through different funding channels. The study argued that investment decisions are influenced by the diversity of financial pathways linking savers and investors, including debt versus equity financing and retained versus distributed earnings. Due to variations in tax treatment across these channels, effective tax rates differ, thereby affecting investment incentives unevenly. The study concluded that the complexity and heterogeneity of financial arrangements dilute the overall impact of corporate tax reforms on investment behaviour.

Focusing specifically on the telecommunications sector, Anika and Obidimma (2021) examined the multiplicity of taxes imposed on telecom operators in Nigeria and the associated regulatory challenges. The study highlighted the absence of sector-specific tax legislation, resulting in

overlapping taxes and regulatory inefficiencies. It argued that excessive and uncoordinated taxation undermines the growth and sustainability of the telecommunications industry, despite its critical role in economic development. The authors advocated for a harmonised and sector-sensitive tax framework that balances government revenue objectives with industry viability.

In a critical review, Nwabachili (2020) analysed the provisions of the Companies Income Tax Act and their implications for investment in Nigeria. The study posited that an inverse relationship exists between taxation and investment, arguing that excessive tax burdens can stifle private sector growth and reduce overall economic productivity. While acknowledging recent reforms introduced through the Finance Act, the study maintained that certain provisions of the tax regime continue to pose constraints on investment. It called for a more balanced approach to taxation that supports both revenue generation and investment promotion.

Overall, the empirical literature reveals no unanimous consensus on the impact of taxation on corporate investment. While several studies report a negative relationship between CIT, VAT, and investment, others highlight context-specific and mixed effects depending on the structure of the tax system, macroeconomic conditions, and firm-level characteristics. This divergence underscores the need for sector-specific analysis, particularly in capital-intensive industries such as telecommunications, where taxation interacts with other critical factors such as infrastructure, regulation, and access to finance.

Methodology

This study employs a quantitative research design, which is considered appropriate for examining the statistical relationship between taxation variables and corporate investment within the Nigerian telecommunications industry. The choice of this design is informed by its suitability for objective measurement, hypothesis testing, and the application of econometric techniques in analysing financial and economic data.

The population of the study comprises all communication companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31st December 2022. Using a purposive sampling technique, the study selects eight (8) firms based on data availability and relevance to the research objectives.

These companies include Airtel Africa Plc, Briclink Africa Plc, Chams Holding Company Plc, CWG Plc, E-Tranzact International Plc, MTN Nigeria Communications Plc, NCR (Nigeria) Plc, and Omatek Ventures Plc. The purposive approach ensures that only firms with consistent and reliable financial data are included in the analysis, thereby enhancing the validity of the findings.

Data for the study are sourced from secondary materials, including annual financial statements of the selected companies, industry reports, published journal articles, and other relevant documentary sources. These data provide information on key variables such as Company Income Tax (CIT), Value Added Tax (VAT), and corporate investment proxies.

For data analysis, the study adopts a multiple regression model to examine the effect of taxation on corporate investment. The model is estimated using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique, which is widely used in empirical financial research due to its efficiency and ease of interpretation. The OLS method enables the estimation of the magnitude and direction of the relationship between the dependent variable (corporate investment) and independent variables (CIT and VAT), while also allowing for statistical testing of the formulated hypotheses.

Results and Presentation of Data

Table 1: The descriptive statistics of the study

	PIT	CIT	VAT	NITDL	CUEXDU
Mean	36.50	677.85	518.43	5.90	170.55
Median	33.03	289.55	272.65	0.15	31.40
Maximum	110.00	3348.75	2924.81	26.97	1605.17
Minimum	13.80	12.30	7.30	0.00	0.00
Std. Dev.	17.60	829.26	640.62	7.89	356.91
Skewness	2.39	1.622	2.20	1.15	2.77

Kurtosis	11.20	5.317	8.27	3.29	10.48
Jarque-Bera	112.64	19.86	58.91	6.75	108.37
Probability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00
Observations	30	30	30	30	30

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 10, 2025

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables of the study. The Company Income Tax (CIT) with the mean of 677.85, median of 289.55 which is positively skewed (1.622) exhibits leptokurtic kurtosis as the value was greater than 3 (5.317). with the result of Jarque-Bera Test of (p-value = 0.00), the null hypothesis of normality was as well rejected. In conclusion, CIT values display a wider range, with a higher mean compared to the median. The positive skewness and leptokurtic distribution indicated a concentration of values around the median, with a few extreme values.

Similarly, Value added tax (VAT) also had the mean of 518.43, median of 272.65 with a positive skewness of 2.20 and 8.27 leptokurtic kurtosis. the Jarque-Bera Test result (p-value = 0.00) to reject null hypothesis of normality was accepted. This revealed that VAT values showed a similar pattern to CIT, with a higher mean compared to the median. The positive skewness and leptokurtic distribution indicated a concentration of values around the median, with a few extreme values in the distribution.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	PIT	CIT	VAT	NITDL	CUEXDU
PIT	1.0000				
CIT	-0.2885	1.0000			
VAT	-0.2559	0.9532	1.0000		
NITDL	-0.2979	0.9711	0.9041	1.0000	

CUEXDU	-0.2976	0.6703	0.4925	0.7003	1.0000
--------	---------	--------	--------	--------	--------

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 10, 2025

This analysis examined the correlation matrix of six variables in Table 2: Private Investment in Telecommunications (PIT), Corporate Income Tax (CIT), and Value-Added Tax (VAT). It examined the correlation coefficients, identify significant relationships, and discuss the implications.

Correlation coefficients range from -1 to 1, where: 1 indicates a perfect positive linear relationship, -1 indicates a perfect negative linear relationship and 0 indicates no linear relationship. The correlation matrix revealed an inverse relationship between private investment of telecommunications (PIT) and company income tax (CIT) and also PIT to value added tax (VAT). The correlation coefficient between PIT and CIT is -0.2885 (29 percent), indicating a moderate negative linear relationship. Similarly, the correlation coefficient between PIT and VAT is -0.2559 (26 percent), also indicating a moderate negative linear relationship. This suggests that changes in PIT are associated with opposite changes in company income tax and value added tax.

For direct relationship, the correlation matrix reveals several significant correlations between company income tax (CIT) and value added tax (VAT). The correlation coefficient between CIT and VAT is 0.9532 (95 percent), indicating a strong positive linear relationship. This suggested that changes in CIT are closely associated with changes in VAT. The correlation coefficient between CIT and NITDL is 0.9711(97 percent), indicating a very strong positive linear relationship. This means that changes in CIT are highly associated with changes in NITDL. The correlation coefficient between VAT and NITDL is 0.9041 (90 percent), indicating a strong direct linear relationship. This confirmed that changes in VAT are closely associated with changes in NITDL.

The correlation matrix analysis provided valuable insights into the relationships between the variables. The strong positive correlations between CIT, VAT, and NITDL revealed that these variables are directly related and may be influenced by similar factors as depicted in table 4.2. The negative correlations among PIT and CIT/VAT showed that PIT may be influenced by different factors outside the model or may have an opposite effect on this study.

Analysis of Research Questions

What is the effect of Companies Income Tax (CIT) on the corporate investment of information and telecommunication companies in Nigeria?

The coefficient of LOG(CIT) is -0.207529, indicating a negative relationship between CIT and corporate investment. However, the p-value (0.5383) is greater than 0.05, suggesting that the effect is not statistically significant.

How does Value Added Tax (VAT) affect the corporate investment of information and telecommunication companies in Nigeria?

The coefficient of LOG(VAT) is 0.322143, indicating a positive relationship between VAT and corporate investment. However, the p-value (0.3462) is greater than 0.05, suggesting that the effect is not statistically significant.

Presentation of Data - Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of companies Income Tax (CIT) on the corporate investment of information and telecommunication companies in Nigeria

The coefficient of log CIT is -0.207529, indicating that a 1% increase in CIT is associated with a 0.21% decrease in corporate investments. Nevertheless, the p-value of 0.5383 is greater than the significance level of 0.05, signifying that the relationship between CIT and corporate investments is not statistically significant. Consequently, we fail to reject the null hypothesis of no significant effect of CIT on corporate investments. This finding advocates that CIT may not have a significant impact on corporate investments in the information and telecommunication sector in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Value Added Tax (VAT) has no significant effect on the corporate investment of information and telecommunication companies in Nigeria.

Given the coefficient of the log the value added tax (VAT), which is 0.322143, indicated that a 1% increase in VAT is associated with a 0.32% increase in corporate investments. Though, given the p-value of 0.3462, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05, indicated that the relationship between VAT and corporate investments is not statistically significant. Thus, the null

hypothesis that there is no significant effect of VAT on corporate investments is accepted. This finding suggested that VAT may not have a significant impact on corporate investments in the information and telecommunication sector in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The empirical results of this study reveal a negative but statistically insignificant relationship between Company Income Tax (CIT) and corporate investment in the Nigerian telecommunications sector. Specifically, the regression outcome indicates that a 1% increase in CIT is associated with approximately a 0.21% decline in corporate investment. Although this relationship aligns with theoretical expectations particularly the distortionary effect of corporate taxation on investment decisions it lacks statistical significance, suggesting that CIT alone may not be a dominant determinant of investment behaviour in the sector. This finding is consistent with prior empirical evidence such as Amahalu (2020), which also reported an inverse relationship between corporate taxation and investment. The implication is that while higher corporate taxes may reduce retained earnings and internal financing capacity, telecommunications firms may be influenced more strongly by other structural and macroeconomic factors such as market size, infrastructure demands, and regulatory conditions.

In contrast, the study finds a positive but statistically insignificant relationship between Value Added Tax (VAT) and corporate investment. The estimated coefficient suggests that a 1% increase in VAT corresponds to a 0.32% increase in corporate investment. This seemingly counterintuitive result may be explained by the consumption-based nature of VAT, which is typically borne by final consumers rather than firms. As a result, telecommunications companies may pass the tax burden to consumers through pricing mechanisms, thereby mitigating its direct impact on investment decisions. Furthermore, the positive association could reflect increased economic activity and consumption patterns, which may indirectly stimulate investment in network expansion and service delivery.

Notwithstanding these observed relationships, the lack of statistical significance in both cases indicates that taxation variables CIT and VAT do not exert a strong explanatory influence on

corporate investment within the Nigerian telecommunications industry during the study period. This suggests that investment decisions in the sector are likely driven by a broader set of factors, including access to finance, exchange rate volatility, inflationary pressures, technological advancements, and the regulatory environment.

The findings also reinforce the mixed evidence documented in the literature. While some studies (e.g., Agbarakwe, 2019; Babu et al., 2020) report significant negative effects of taxation on investment, others (e.g., Yusuf & Mohd, 2020; Turakpe et al., 2020) identify positive or insignificant relationships depending on the tax type, model specification, and economic context. This divergence underscores the complexity of taxation-investment dynamics and suggests that the impact of tax policy is context-specific and mediated by institutional and macroeconomic conditions.

Overall, the study contributes to the ongoing discourse by highlighting that, within the Nigerian telecommunications sector, taxation may not be the most critical constraint on corporate investment. Instead, a more holistic policy approach that addresses structural bottlenecks and enhances the business environment may yield more substantial investment outcomes.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the impact of Company Income Tax (CIT) and Value Added Tax (VAT) on corporate investment within the Nigerian telecommunications industry, a sector widely acknowledged as a critical driver of economic growth, digital transformation, and financial inclusion. Drawing on empirical analysis, the study established that CIT exhibits a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with corporate investment, while VAT demonstrates a positive but similarly insignificant relationship. These findings imply that although increases in CIT may potentially discourage investment by reducing firms' retained earnings and internal financing capacity, and VAT may indirectly support investment through consumption-driven demand, neither tax instrument exerts a statistically significant influence on investment decisions within the sector during the period under review.

The results align with extant empirical literature. For instance, Amahalu (2020) reported a negative association between CIT and corporate investment, while Akinola and Akinrinola (2023) identified a positive relationship between VAT and investment. However, the insignificance of the coefficients in this study suggests that taxation, though theoretically relevant, may not be the dominant factor influencing corporate investment behaviour in Nigeria's telecommunications industry. Instead, investment decisions appear to be shaped more strongly by macroeconomic and structural variables such as inflationary trends, exchange rate volatility, infrastructural deficits, regulatory uncertainties, access to long-term financing, and the overall ease of doing business.

Accordingly, the study concludes that while taxation remains an important component of fiscal policy and revenue generation, its direct effect on corporate investment in the Nigerian telecommunications sector is limited in practical terms. This underscores the need for a broader policy perspective that goes beyond tax adjustments to address the underlying constraints to investment and sectoral growth.

Recommendations

i. Policy Makers:

Government and fiscal authorities should adopt a balanced and strategic approach to tax policy formulation. While maintaining an efficient tax system is essential for revenue mobilisation, excessive focus on tax rates alone may not yield the desired investment outcomes. Policymakers should prioritise tax stability, transparency, and predictability, as these are critical to investor confidence. In addition, efforts should be made to streamline the multiplicity of taxes and levies imposed on telecommunications firms across federal, state, and local levels to reduce the burden of compliance and eliminate distortions in the business environment.

ii. Corporate Investors and Industry Operators:

Investors and telecommunications firms should consider taxation as only one of several factors influencing investment decisions. Greater emphasis should be placed on strategic considerations such as market expansion opportunities, technological innovation, cost efficiency, and risk

management. Firms should also adopt robust tax planning strategies within the ambit of the law to optimise their tax positions without undermining compliance obligations.

iii. Government Intervention and Structural Reforms:

The government should focus on improving the broader investment climate by addressing key structural challenges. Priority areas include the provision of critical infrastructure (such as power supply and broadband backbone networks), enhancement of security, and the establishment of a stable and investor-friendly regulatory framework. Strengthening access to finance through capital market development and targeted incentives for infrastructure investment will also play a significant role in stimulating corporate investment.

iv. Regulatory and Institutional Framework:

Regulatory agencies should work collaboratively to ensure policy coherence and reduce regulatory bottlenecks in the telecommunications sector. A clear, consistent, and technology-responsive regulatory regime will encourage long-term investment and innovation.

v. Future Research:

Further studies should incorporate additional variables such as interest rates, exchange rates, inflation, and firm-specific characteristics to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of corporate investment. Expanding the dataset and adopting alternative econometric techniques may also yield deeper insights into the taxation-investment nexus in Nigeria and other developing economies.

References

- Adefunke, A. B., & Usiomon, A. O. (2022). Impact of company income tax on corporate profitability in Nigeria. *Indian Journal of Finance and Banking*, 9(1), 104–114.
- Adegbite, T. A., & Akande, S. S. (2017). The impact of value added tax on private investment in Nigeria. *Account and Financial Management Journal*, 2(4), 644–651.

- Adeyeye, G. B. (2019). Improving tax administration through technology innovation in Nigeria: A study of the Federal Inland Revenue Service. *Annals of Spiru Haret University Economic Series*, 19(1), 31–64.
- Agbarakwe, W. C. (2019). An empirical assessment of the impact of corporate tax on private sector investment and economic development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Economics*, 7(1), 1–12.
- Ajagun, O. (2021). Disruptive technology and value-added tax in selected telecommunication companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Reviews*, 11(1), 135–150.
- Ajala, O. O. M., & Adegbe, F. F. (2020). Effects of information technology on effective tax assessment in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 12(4), 126–134.
- Akadakpo, B. A., & Akogo, O. U. (2022). Impact of company income tax on corporate profitability in Nigeria. *Indian Journal of Finance and Banking*, 9(1), 104–114.
- Akinola, O. M., & Akinrinola, O. (2023). Impact of tax revenue and infrastructural development on economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics, Management and Trade*, 29(3), 1–15.
- Amahalu, N. (2020). Effect of taxes on net investment of listed communication firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 10(2), 171–183.
- Anika, E. A., & Obidimma, A. E. (2021). Taxing telecommunications companies in Nigeria: Legal challenges in the telecommunications industry. *International Review of Law and Jurisprudence*, 3(1), 206–211.
- Anyaduba, J. O., & Otulugbu, P. O. (2019). Taxation and income inequality in Nigeria. *Accounting and Finance Research*, 8(3), 118–135.
- Anyira, I. E., & Idubor, I. (2020). Role of education and libraries in developing Nigeria's knowledge economy. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1–17.
- Babu, W. A., Pantaleo, I. M., & Ndanshau, M. O. A. (2020). Econometric analysis of the impact of taxes on private investment in Sub-Saharan Africa. *African Journal of Economic Review*, 8(1), 176–197.
- Ballesyerros, S., & Goda, T. (2020). The impact of effective corporate tax rates on investment. *Documentos de Trabajo Economía y Finanzas*, 20(18), 1–21.

- Dodge, J. M. (2005). Theories of tax justice: Ruminations on the benefit, partnership, and ability-to-pay principles. *Tax Law Review*, 58, 399–453.
- Dougherty, S., Harding, M., & Reschovsky, A. (2019). Twenty years of tax autonomy across levels of government: Measurement and applications. *OECD Working Papers on Fiscal Federalism*, 29.
- Egbuhuzor, C. A., & Adokiye, I. T. (2021). Effect of indirect taxes on economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 7(1), 1–10.
- Eme, O. I., Chukwurah, D. C., & Iheanacho, E. N. (2015). An analysis of pros and cons of treasury single account policy in Nigeria. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 5(4), 20–30.
- Freebairn, J. (2022). Company income tax and business investment. *Australian Economic Review*, 55(3), 346–360.
- Hayes, A. (2023). Investment basics explained with types to invest in. *Investopedia*. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/investment.asp>
- Irefe-Esema, J., & Akinmade, B. (2020). Automation and tax compliance: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Business*, 8(3), 45–58.
- Jangilli, R., & Kumar, S. (2010). Determinants of corporate sector investment in India. *MPRA Paper No. 39834*.
- Jensen, M. C. (1986). Agency costs of free cash flow, corporate finance, and takeovers. *The American Economic Review*, 76(2), 323–329.
- Kjærsgaard, L. F. (2021). The ability to pay and economic allegiance: Justifying additional allocation of taxing rights to market states. *Intertax*, 49(8/9), 636–650.
- Kujore, O. A., Dada, S. O., & Adegbe, F. F. (2021). Tax revenue and economic growth of the telecommunication sector in Nigeria (2001–2018). *International Journal of Research Science and Management*, 8(8), 11–21.
- Laura, U. A. (2019). Impact of indirect taxation on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Science*, 6(5), 54–61.
- Njuguna, T. W., Iraya, C., Nyamute, W., & Kiiru, J. (2022). Cash flow volatility, corporate investments and value of non-financial firms listed in Kenya. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 7(4), 182–191.

- Nnubia, I. C., Okafor, G. O., Chukwunwike, O. D., Asogwa, O. S., & Ogan, R. J. (2020). Effect of e-taxation on revenue generation in Nigeria: A pre-post analysis. *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 26(3), 1–19.
- Nwabachili, C. O. (2020). Critique of company income tax act and its impact on investments in Nigeria. *Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence*, 11(2), 34–43.
- Nwokenkwo, B. (2017). An appraisal of the efficiency of local tax administration in Nigeria. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Construction and Real Estate Management (ICCREM 2016)* (pp. 770–781).
- Obi, C. K., & Ifelunini, I. (2019). Mobilization of domestic resources for economic development financing in Nigeria: Does tax matter? *Scientific Papers of the University of Pardubice, Faculty of Economics and Administration*, 27(45), 113–125.
- Odunsi, O. T. (2022). Value added tax, revenue generation and growth in Nigeria. *ACU Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 3(1), 201–211.
- Ojeka, S. A. (2011). Tax policy and the growth of SMEs: Implications for the Nigerian economy. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 2(2), 16–26.
- Oladele, R., Aribaba, F. O., Adekunle, A. R., & Babatunde, A. D. (2020). E-tax administration and tax compliance among corporate taxpayers in Nigeria. *Accounting and Taxation Review*, 4(3), 93–101.
- Oladipo, O. A., Iyoha, A., Fakile, S. A., Asaleye, A. J., & Eluyela, F. D. (2019). Do government taxes have implications on manufacturing sector output? Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Management Information and Decision Sciences*, 22(3), 181–190.
- Olatunji, O. C., & Oluwatoyin, A. E. (2019). Effect of corporate taxation on the profitability of firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 11, 191–201.
- Opoku, E. E. O., Muazu, I., & Yakubu, A. S. (2019). Foreign direct investment, sectoral effects and economic growth in Africa. *International Economic Journal*, 33(3), 473–492.
- Oraka, A. O., Okegbe, T. O., & Ezejiofor, R. A. (2017). Effect of value added tax on the Nigerian economy. *European Academic Research*, 5(2), 1185–1223.
- Osho, A. E., & Efuntade, A. O. (2019). Impact of taxation on investment, social and economic development in Nigeria. *Global Scientific Journal*, 7(11), 44–60.
- Ososukpor, J. O. (2016). *Determinants of corporate investment in Nigeria: Application of the real option theory* (Doctoral dissertation, Delta State University).

- Oyigbo, D. N., Ngwu, P. N. C., & Nwachukwu, R. U. (2021). Non-formal education and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Review of Education*, 67(1), 687–709.
- Panagiotidis, T., & Printzis, P. (2021). Investment and uncertainty: Are large firms different from small ones? *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 184, 302–317.
- Rasheed, I. O., & Lateef, F. K. (2023). Corporate taxes and financial performance of listed ICT companies in Nigeria. *African Journal of Accounting and Financial Research*, 4(6), 160–176.
- Sankarganesh, K. R., & Shanmugam, K. R. (2023). Effect of corporate income tax on investment decisions of Indian manufacturing firms. *Journal of the Asia Pacific Economy*, 28(1), 156–175.
- Sarka, S. W., & Ibrahim, M. (2019). The role of taxation in national development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Development and Policy Studies*, 7(4), 66–76.
- Stantcheva, S. (2021). Understanding tax policy: How do people reason? *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 136(4), 2309–2369.
- Taiwo, A. O., & Oyedokun, G. E. (2022). Corporate taxes and financial performance of SMEs in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 2(3), 107–122.
- Turakpe, M. J., Azoroh, B. J., Tordee, B., & Effe-Nnamdi, A. (2020). The effect of taxation on investors' performance in Nigeria. *Equatorial Journal of Finance and Management Sciences*, 3(2), 44–56.
- Umukoro, I. O., Omolade-Lawal, A. O., Babalola, S. O., Akinsumbo, K. S., Aligwa, R. M., & Abdul-Jeleel, B. A. (2021). Gender differences in access to and use of ICTs in Nigeria. In *Encyclopedia of Information Science and Technology* (5th ed., pp. 1699–1718). IGI Global.
- Yuelan, P., Akbar, M. W., Hafeez, M., Ahmad, M., Zia, Z., & Ullah, S. (2019). The nexus of fiscal policy instruments and environmental degradation in China. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 26, 28919–28932.
- Yusuf, A., & Mohd, S. (2020). An econometric analysis of the impact of taxation on domestic investment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Financial Management and Economics*, 3(1), 32–38.